

Organization Of Physical Education Lessons And After-Lesson Club Activities In Inclusive Education

Olimjon Shodiev

Director of the Institute of Retraining and Advanced Training
of Adaptive Physical Education and Sports Specialists.

olimjonshodiyev2020@gmail.com

Abstract. This article analyzes the importance of physical education classes and after-school clubs in educational organizations with inclusive education, as well as current problems in organizing the process of classes and clubs. Proposals and recommendations have been developed to create full-fledged conditions for young people with disabilities to engage in adaptive physical education and sports in educational organizations.

Keywords: Inclusive education, person with disabilities, adaptive, adaptive physical education, adaptive sports, club classes, harmonization, rehabilitation, humane society.

INTRODUCTION

The main goal of the modern education system is to prepare young people as worthy successors for tomorrow. Along with healthy young people, it is necessary to provide education to young people who want to get an education, despite their physical limitations.

In recent years, our country has taken the necessary measures to further improve the system of support for people with disabilities and strengthen their position in society based on the principle of "For the sake of human dignity".

It is an important task to ensure the consistency and systematicity of reforms in this area, to further improve the conditions created for the education of children with disabilities, to promote their adaptation to society and to bring the work on support to a new level.

This goal is duly reflected in many laws of our republic, a number of documents of our government, including the speeches, reports and speeches, decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev. In particular, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the laws "On Physical Education and

Sports", "On Education", "On the Rights of Persons with Disabilities", the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 1, 2023 No. PF-82 "On comprehensive measures to provide high-quality social services and assistance to the population and establish an effective control system for them", the resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 13, 2020 No. PQ-4860 "On measures to further improve the system of education and upbringing of children with special educational needs", the resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 8, 2024 No. PQ-389 "On additional measures to improve the system of physical rehabilitation through involving persons with disabilities in sports", Resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 638 dated October 12, 2021 "On approval of regulatory legal acts on education of children with special educational needs", No. 599 dated October 14, 2022 "On measures to organize the activities of the Institute for the Training of Paralympic Sports Specialists under the National Paralympic Committee of Uzbekistan", No. 46 dated January 25, 2024 "On measures to organize the education of children with special educational

needs and improve their rehabilitation system” provide a number of instructions for the effective organization of work on establishing inclusive education and creating the necessary conditions for them [1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10].

We observe that this law and its subordinate legal acts pay great attention to strengthening the social protection of the population, realizing the rights of persons with disabilities, providing them with material, moral, and social support, and stipulate that in order to restore the health of persons with disabilities and rehabilitate them, the provision of auxiliary medical and technical means, the adaptation of educational institution buildings for students with disabilities, the creation of the necessary material and technical base, the provision of qualified personnel, the creation of educational and methodological literature, the development and wide promotion of inclusive education, and a number of other works will be carried out. In recent years, inclusive education, which has been increasingly recognized by the world community, is aimed at ensuring the freedom of each child to choose the type of education, the right to be in a family, to grow up in their own home and neighborhood, and to receive education equally for all. These factors indicate the importance of studying the problem of inclusive education, the process of special education and upbringing of students with disabilities.

Research objective. To effectively establish a system for improving the quality and effectiveness of scientifically based and properly organized adaptive physical education lessons for students with disabilities in educational organizations where inclusive education is organized, as well as to develop scientifically based proposals and recommendations for improving the knowledge and skills of physical education teachers in adaptive physical education and sports, effectively organizing inclusion in physical education lessons,

and organizing and organizing after-school clubs for students with disabilities in sports of their choice and suitability.

Research objectives.

- To develop scientific conclusions based on the results of the study of the conditions created for the participation of healthy students and students with disabilities in physical education classes in educational organizations where inclusive education is organized, and the provision of appropriate sports equipment and equipment.

- To identify mechanisms for increasing the interest and popularity of students with disabilities in adaptive physical education and sports activities in educational organizations where inclusive education is organized;

- To search for measures to improve the system of training, retraining and advanced training of qualified specialists who provide education and training in adaptive physical education and sports activities for students with disabilities and disabilities in educational organizations where inclusive education is organized and planned to be established in the future;

- To study the possibilities of cooperation between students with disabilities and disabilities, healthy students, physical education teachers, the educational organization team, and parents.

Research method. In educational organizations with inclusive education in Tashkent city and Tashkent region, the participation of students with disabilities in adaptive physical education classes along with healthy children, their interest in the subject, and the processes of physical education teachers conducting adaptive physical education classes for students with disabilities were studied.

At the same time, the organization of adaptive sports clubs and the involvement of students in adaptive sports classes and after-school clubs for students with disabilities in educational

organizations with inclusive education were analyzed.

In this regard, the participation of students with physical disabilities and students with disabilities in adaptive physical education classes and after-school clubs, the conditions created for them and the provision of sports facilities, necessary sports equipment, and teachers were studied. The opinions and experiences of leading specialists in the field were also taken into account.

Research results and discussion.

Scientifically based and properly organized adaptive physical education of students with disabilities in educational organizations with inclusive education has a beneficial effect on the young organism: it allows for comprehensive physical and mental development, expands the possibilities of movement, increases protective adaptive reactions, increases the body's resistance to adverse effects of external factors, and also gives children and adolescents cheerfulness, vigor, and fosters feelings of patriotism and love for the Motherland.

Physical education and sports include three main areas of knowledge that are interconnected - physical education, medicine and correctional pedagogy. All three areas help to set specific goals and objectives for restoring the potential of students with disabilities, but we must not forget that the restoration of lost abilities is individual for each specific person.

The main focus of the research is on the specific characteristics of each class at the level of current requirements, taking into account their age, medical, psychological and other conditions. Also, taking into account the most important issues, taking into account the age characteristics of students, the formation of their movements, skills and qualifications, the development of movement qualities in the work method (training in a circular manner, independent practice of physical education

and training methods, accurate and thorough completion of homework, regular habituation to a healthy lifestyle), the use of physical exercises, and the methodological study of types of programs. The analysis of the teacher's focus on solving specific tasks, decisions and goals of adaptive physical education in the distribution of the curriculum is carried out.

Adaptive physical education is developing rather slowly in educational organizations with inclusive education in our country, not to mention its presence within the framework of school education. If we compare the level of development of physical education in the world, the leading places are, of course, occupied by European countries. This is primarily due to the fact that the level of humanization of society and the provision of necessary equipment are much higher there.

Therefore, one of the tasks of the Uzbek education system is to develop this type of physical education. The task is not easy, but it has great potential.

Despite the created good regulatory and legal framework, there are many problems in physical education and sports that require special attention:

- the problem of the shortage of personnel who are willing and able to work with students with disabilities. After all, students with disabilities need not only special care, but also spiritual and medical support. There are not enough higher educational institutions in this field in our country, and young specialists who have just graduated from those that exist cannot provide sufficient assistance to people with disabilities. In this regard, specialists must constantly improve their knowledge, as well as regularly increase the level of practical and theoretical knowledge in this field [12].

- this is a low material and technical base, expressed in the lack of special equipment and low territorial accessibility. Specialized institutions are usually few in number, located in large cities and do not meet modern minimum requirements. It is almost

impossible for people with disabilities living in rural areas to attend classes [7].

- the lack of a comprehensive and systematic approach to creating adaptive physical education programs and high-quality advertising in social networks;

- the reluctance of students with physical disabilities and disabilities to engage in adaptive physical education and sports on their own;

It is necessary to solve the problems of introducing adaptive physical education in educational organizations with inclusive education, as this has a positive effect on the physical and psychological health of students with physical disabilities and disabilities, as well as on their socialization in society.

Based on the listed problems in the implementation of adaptive physical education and sports in educational organizations with inclusive education, the main priority areas for their elimination can be identified:

Firstly, to expand the information space at various levels of the state, primarily through the media, in order to attract as many students with disabilities as possible to physical education and mass sports;

Secondly, to ensure the organization of inclusive education in educational organizations for young people with disabilities living in remote areas and to organize transport infrastructure;

Thirdly, to provide educational organizations with the necessary personnel, as well as to ensure the training, advanced training and retraining of existing specialists who are ready to work with young people with disabilities;

Fourthly, to create a material, technical, regulatory and legal framework and provide targeted financing for all the needs necessary for the development of adaptive physical education and sports for young people with disabilities in our country.

Fifthly, to attract specialists in adaptive physical education and health, create good working

conditions for them and the opportunity to develop individual programs;

Sixthly, to allocate more funds for equipment that allows children with disabilities and individuals with special educational needs to study safely;

Seventhly, to organize a comprehensive and systematic approach to creating programs for the introduction of adaptive physical education by holding meetings and conferences with specialists in this field;

Eighth, organize control and monitoring of the concept of developing adaptive physical education and sports among students with disabilities.

Solving these problems requires the joint efforts of the state, non-governmental non-profit organizations, sports clubs, specialists in the field of adaptive physical education and sports, as well as the public. It is necessary to carry out explanatory work among the general population, improve access to infrastructure, improve the skills of teachers, provide material assistance, and actively combat the problem.

Conclusion. Increasing the effectiveness of adaptive physical education classes will allow raising the entire system of complex rehabilitation of schoolchildren with physical education, education, and health problems to a new quality level, improving their standard of living and relationships in society. The presence of various diagnoses in children requires constant awareness, caution, and hard work from the teacher, who must periodically study new and appropriate training options, review standards and tasks.

Physical education plays an important role in the maturation and development of a person as a person. This method of education teaches movement, endurance and provides an opportunity to master physical education knowledge. Physical education and sports are very important for all children in educational organizations, as well as for children with disabilities. Therefore, we must

continue to develop such an educational direction (in terms of quality and quantity) in our country as adaptive physical education and sports.

Properly organized inclusive education serves to prevent discrimination against such children, to support the right of children with special needs to a decent life, free development, and to be equal members of society.

References.

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. // National database of legislative documents, 01.05.2023, No. 03/23/837/0241.
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Physical Education and Sports” T.: September 4, 2015.
3. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education”. // National database of legislative documents, 24.09.2020, No. 03/20/637/1313.
4. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Rights of Persons with Disabilities” T.: October 15, 2020.
5. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-82 dated June 1, 2023 “On comprehensive measures to provide high-quality social services and assistance to the population and establish an effective control system for them”,
6. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4860 dated October 13, 2020 “On measures to further improve the system of education and upbringing of children with special educational needs”.
7. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-389 dated November 8, 2024 “On additional measures to improve the system of physical rehabilitation through involving persons with disabilities in sports”.
8. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 638 dated October 12, 2021 “On approval of regulatory legal acts on the education of children with special educational needs”.
9. Resolution No. 599 dated October 14, 2022 “On measures to organize the activities of the Institute

for the Training of Paralympic Sports Specialists under the National Paralympic Committee of Uzbekistan”.

10. Resolution No. 46 dated January 25, 2024 “On measures to improve the system of organizing the education of children with special educational needs and their rehabilitation”.

11. Technology of physical and sports activities and adaptive physical culture: teacher's book / O.E. Yevseyeva, S.P. Yevseyev. - Moscow: Sport, 2016.

12. Mamarajabova Z.N, Subanova B.Q. Inclusive education (in the case of hearing-impaired children): study guide / - Tashkent, 2022.